

Empowerment of Women through Panchayati Raj Institutions

M.Aarthy

Scholar, Department of Political Science
Madurai Kamaraj University, Madurai

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Abstract

Women have had a long of being discriminated against and exploited in Indian society. The 73rd constitutional Amendment introduced measures to reverse these indignities. yet, there remains strong resistance against their participation in the public sphere. Empowerment of women is essentially the process of upliftment of economic, social and political status of women, the traditionally underprivileged ones, in the society. It involves the building up of a society wherein women can breathe without the fear of oppression, exploitation, apprehension, discrimination and the general feeling of persecution which goes with being a women in a traditionally male dominated structure, political participation of women can be viewed as one of the proven strategies for the empowerment of women. Panchayet being the nearest form of government to the people can play instrumental role in their empowerment by ensuring effective participation of them. The 73rd constitutional Amendment ushered in a major change in the history of Panchayet making provision for the reservation of women. But a number of studies have proved that reservation alone cannot ensure participation of women in political decision making process leading towards their empowerment. Though it has made a positive impact but still there is long way to go, A concerted effort from multiple government and non- government actors including CSOs and media has to be made by adopting multi-pronged strategies to achieve that goal. This paper has made an attempt to analyse the concept of empowerment, how to measure it, strategies for empowerment of women and assess the role of Panchayet in participation as well as empowerment of women and also suggest some effective measures to achieve that goal.

Keywords: women, panchayati raj, empowerment, discrimination, government, reservation.

Introduction

India is the second largest populated country in the world where nearly 701 percent of the population lives in rural area .women constitute an intedral part of rural india as 405.83 million or 48.69 percent of the rural people are women. But in india women have been deprived of various kinds of opportunites and advantages by our traditional society for the past several countries. The women were marginalised from the public sphere and most of the decisions are taken by the male dominated power structure in the society. Various initiatives are taken to improve the status of women in independent India.

Democracy, the form of government adopted in India, proclaims participation of all people in the decision making process. However, it has been seen that though women constitute about half of the

population they are not adequately represented in different institution of the political system. Therefore, the empowerment approach has been followed to provide opportunity to women for taking part in the political process of the country.”women empowerment is the most used and discussed term today. The empowerment of women is becoming an increasingly popular term in human rights in 1959, on Mahatma Gandhi birth anniversary on 2 octomber, the first prime minister of India,pundit Jawaharlal Neru formally launched the new system of panchayati raj at Degana village in Nagaur district Rajasthan. At the same time,a panchayat was created in Andhar Pradesh as well in 1959, Neru led congress party had an overwhelming majority at the union and was ruling in all states. Hence, appropriate legal provisions for panchayats were made all across rural india.

Women Development and Women Empowerment

Female are nearly 50 percent of the total population but their representation in public life is very low. Women continues to bear the major load of the household work,Her primary role is often viewed by society as housewife. The cardinal goals of democracy “of the people, by the people and for the people” cannot the be optimally accomplished if female population remains out of political empowerment. The subordination of women in society sets a structural constraint to their participation in political activities. The constraint operates more or less for all classes and communities of women. The prevalent culture is very complicated and offen decisions are taken behind the scene may be regarded as another constraint in this regard women empowerment and development.

Empowering women is the basic to the basics of human rights where woman wants neither to beg for power nor search for power to exercise power over others. On the contrary she demands to be accepted as human first of all. She as a person in command of herself and necessarily all the resources physical, social, economical, political, cultural and spiritual to be equally accessible to her, there are prerequisites for considering the whole question of empowerment. Indian society has inherited male chauvinism but now society has started to realize woman’s importance and has accepted woman empowerment, woman as an active agent for development, and guiding her own development.

Women Empowerment in Panchayat Raj Insitutions

In India, attempts at strengthening local democracy have invariably invoked the traditional self governing institutions of the village, which have often been romanticized and valorized by a wide variety of observers, from Henry Maine to Mahatma Gandhi. Historically, however, despite their consensual appearance, these institutions were not really democratic as they were concealed forms of social prejudice, oppression and exploitation that were firmly rooted in local power structures. It was in recognition of these that B.R. Ambedkar argued strenuously in the Constituent Assembly against incorporating them into that Document. This is why the impulse for local self-government, embodied in Article 401, was placed in the non-justiciable Directive Principles of State Policy

After Independence, the idea of the revival of panchayats was first mooted in the Balwantrai Mehta Committee Report (1957), which saw democratic decentralisation as a way of making good the failures of the community development programme. Two decades later, the Asoka Mehta Committee Report on Panchayati Raj Institutions made far reaching recommendations for the revival of panchayats, which inspired at least a few states notably, Karnataka, Kerala and West Bengal to restructure their institutions of local government. At the national level, the initiative to give Constitutional status to Panchayati Raj was attempted by the Rajiv Gandhi government in 1989. Eventually, in 1993, Panchayati Raj was incorporated into the Constitution by the 73rd

(for panchayats at the village, block and district levels) and 74th (for municipalities) Constitutional Amendment Acts.

The next important milestone in the history of Panchayati Raj in India was the Asoka Mehta Committee Report of 1978. Between Balwantrai Mehta and Asoka Mehta, the Committee for the Status of Women in India, in its famous report "Towards Equality" (1974), argued forcefully that rural women's needs and perspectives had never been given sufficient weightage in the plans and development policies of the Government of India. The Report recognised that cooption and nomination were underwritten by the assumption that women were incapable of contesting elections, and would not permit the questioning, much less transformation, of power equations in rural society. It therefore recommended the setting-up of statutory women's panchayats at the local level, which would have strong links with Panchayati Raj institutions, as well as possess some resources to manage and administer welfare and development programmes for women and children.

Constitution (73rd Amendment) Act, 1992

- The reservation of seats for SCs/STs in proportion to the population of SCs/STs in the Panchayat area
- Not less than 1/3rd of the total number of seats reserved under Clause-I shall be reserved for women belonging to SC/ST. empowerment.
- Overall not less than 1/3rd of the total number of seats to be filled by direct election for every Panchayat shall be reserved for women. Seats reserved for women may be rotated to different constituencies in a Panchayat

Women's Reservation Bill

The real test of democracy is the creation of equality of opportunity for the hitherto deprived sections of society. The idea of making legal provision for reserving seats for women in the Parliament and State Assemblies came into being during Rajeev Gandhi's tenure as the Prime Minister of India when the Panchayati Raj Act, 1992 (73rd and 74th Constitutional Amendments) came into effect granting not less than 33% reservation to women in the Panchayati Raj Institutions or local bodies.

Conclusion

Women should be given education. Education will broaden their outlook and make them aware of their rights, duties and responsibilities in the society. An important requirement for bringing about empowerment of rural women is to bring about an attitudinal change in both men and women. The feeling that women are meant for household activities and bearing children needs to be replaced by a feeling of equal partnership of women and men. The reservations at local level and Women's participation in Panchayati Raj institutions are not enough for the Women Empowerment. We have a long way to go, but we will get there someday. Swami Vivekananda had said "That nation which doesn't respect women will never become great now and nor will ever in future and in pursuit of making India a great nation, let us work towards giving women their much deserved status."

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